

Workshop: Current drivers and barriers for the assessment and regulation of Combined Sewer Overflows (CSOs)

Pre-conference Workshop of 9th Int. Conference on Sewer Processes and Networks (SPN9), 26th August 2019, Aalborg, Denmark; by the International Working Group Data and Models (IWGDM)

Jörg Rieckermann*, Eawag, Switzerland; Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski, INSA Lyon, France; Frank Blumensaat, Eawag, Switzerland; Christoph Ort, Eawag, Switzerland; Alberto Pistocchi, JRC Ispra, Italy; Alma Schellart, University of Sheffield, UK.

*corresponding author: joerg.rieckermann@eawag.ch

Revised version 04 March 2020.

For presentation slides and recorded workshop discussions please refer to:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/spn9-cso-workshop/?page=1&size=20>

Introduction

Combined sewer overflows (CSOs) can be a significant source of surface water quality deterioration for four major reasons. First, discontinuous but highly dynamic discharges of organics, nutrients, and water volumes evidently lead to an impaired ecological status in aquatic ecosystems. This impact will be more pronounced due to an increasing urbanisation and more frequent occurrence of extreme events due to a changing climate. Second, several emerging micropollutants, such as microplastics and pesticides, are often stormwater-driven. Third, with progressing urban wastewater treatment, such as the removal of micropollutants of emerging concern, the relative importance of CSOs as a pathway of urban pollution is likely to increase. Finally, people are expecting higher environmental standards, i.e. bathing water quality (Badevand, 2019; Garneau and Vanrolleghem, 2017), and pollution incidents can attract fines (UK Environment Agency, 2019, 2017) as well as significant negative publicity (Carrington, 2017; BBC, 2018).

Triggered by regulation, water utilities are making big investments to mitigate CSO pollution. However, there are hundreds of thousands CSO structures across Europe and it is currently not known whether money is actually spent efficiently and in the right places. The availability of increasingly efficient (low-tech, low-cost, low-power) online monitoring techniques and data evaluation routines is currently changing the way researchers, utilities and regulators are monitoring CSOs. However, in many countries CSO related data is unstructured, not used in compliance assessment, nor well organised or widely shared. **So, although an increasing amount of CSO data is being collected, the amount of useful information on CSO related problems is very limited.** Also, the knowledge on ongoing activities in research and practice is very fragmented. For example, during the review of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD), the *Joint Research Centre* (JRC) in Ispra, Italy has been developing an EU-wide screening model for CSOs for *European Commission* to close the data gap - with mixed success (Pistocchi, 2019). The *Joint Research Centre* is struggling to access enough datasets on CSOs to test and run the model mentioned above (Pistocchi, 2019).

To discuss current drivers and barriers for the assessment and regulation of CSOs, a workshop has been organised by the IWGDM at the SPN9 conference. The goal of the workshop was to collect the opinion of the community and derive a set of specific recommendations to chart a way forward.

As a result of the workshop, the workshop organisers distilled the discussions into the following 4 main recommendations, which may not represent exactly every participant's individual views. More detail is described in the extended summary following the list of recommendations. Finally, an additional recommendation is that the IWGDM should live-stream future meetings and using online polling, to make them more inclusive, by remote participation, and more interactive.

Main workshop recommendations

1) Provide an evidence base on the functioning and the impact of CSOs

a) There is a need for more summarising studies of local bodies of evidence on the functioning and impact of CSOs, as well as Separated Sewer System Outflows (SSOs). This should not only include aggregated performance data, such as e.g. the annual number of spills, spill volumes, usage of tank volume and event-mean concentrations. It should also provide evidence, based on continuous field monitoring data, on the activity of CSOs including the spatial and temporal variability of pollution, allowing for conclusions on potential impacts of CSOs on surface water quality.

b) Submit datasets on catchment characteristics and CSO activity to the *JRC*¹. The data needed for direct model verification of the JRC's EU-wide model to quantify the relevance of CSOs is: area-specific overflow volume in m³/ha/year; CSO volume vs. precipitation; catchment data, such as population density, dry weather flow, proportion of impervious area, and runoff coefficients. Indirect data that would also be useful is: frequency, duration of overflows, and estimates of overflow spills as the fraction of generated wastewater.

2) Develop a culture of evidence-based CSO compliance assessment

a) Develop robust, relevant and cost-effective CSO performance indicators based on field monitoring data. There is an urgent need to perform more field studies and data analyses that link problem-oriented water quality metrics (e.g. O₂ deficits, NH₃ peaks, trace pollutant dynamics) to observable emissions (e.g. duration of spill or volume). Further, there is a need to quantify the levels of uncertainty in deriving such metrics from field monitoring data collected at different space and time scales, or sensors of different levels of accuracy. This enables CSO performance assessment being cost-effective and reliable, i.e. qualified through a designated uncertainty assessment.

b) Establish standard procedures for data collection, data quality checking and data accreditation. Collaborate with stakeholders to develop guidance for data-based assessment.

3) Water utilities should tap the hidden potential of creating value from data

a) Information regarding the occurrence and magnitude of CSOs should be made public, as in the U.S. and Denmark. Data should be shared online to moderated domains, and in ways easy to interpret, so as to foster more public engagement and participation.

b) Gather more evidence for utilities on the potential benefits of sharing and further analysing field monitoring data. For example, water levels in tanks can provide a basis for plausibility checks of rainfall-runoff models, which in turn ensure good decision support in long-term urban drainage planning.

c) Develop pilot projects to collect information on CSO performance into a central database. This would include conceptual data models as well as standards for (meta)data sharing, e.g. with the Norman database (Norman, 2019) as a potentially suited infrastructure. Carry out research into what

¹ Get in touch with Alberto Pistocchi via e-mail (Alberto.PISTOCCHI@ec.europa.eu) for further details.

type of data should be shared, with what level of aggregation and with what levels of access, and how such a database might be funded and sustained in the longer term.

4) The need for addressing non-technical issues

a) Investigate barriers to the adoption of policies related to data gathering and sharing, as well as providing stakeholders with more evidence and demonstration studies showing the benefits of sharing monitoring data, e.g. through benchmarking.

b) The revision of the UWWTD should include regulations for CSOs. Any new regulation should permit to test new methodologies; regulations which reinforce inflexible *status quo* practices should be avoided. Instead, authorities should rather develop incentives to adopt an integrated view on the wastewater system. Jointly optimising drainage system and Waste Water Treatment Plant (WWTP) performance is beneficial (Erbe *et al.*, 2002; Meng *et al.*, 2016; Schütze *et al.*, 2004; Seggelke *et al.*, 2013; Vanrolleghem *et al.*, 2005), because the functioning of drainage networks is inherently sensitive to the wet weather treatment capacity of WWTP, affecting both the overflow and the treatment performance. Currently, there are almost no regulatory incentives to maximise wet weather inflows into WWTPs, nor avoid premature emptying of stored combined sewage volumes or adopt source control measures. There are no proven concepts how to regulate such a joint system with limited data (Meng *et al.*, 2016).

c) Thoroughly investigate the cost-effectiveness of CSO as water pollution control. This should not only take into account the net present value, but also include the benefit of flexibility, i.e. the possibility to adapt infrastructure to a changing climate or socio-economic boundary conditions.

Extended workshop summary

Why the need to provide an evidence base on the functioning and impact of CSOs?

At European scale it is currently questioned what percentage of generated wastewater is treated by WWTPs, and what percentage is discharged into receiving waters via CSOs (Milieu, 2016; Pistocchi, 2019; Woods-Ballard and Cherrier, 2019). This question is challenging *per se*, but even more difficult to answer because data on the functioning of CSOs on the regional or national level is sparse and inconsistent. Besides number and duration of CSO spills, it is unclear: i) How relevant are CSOs in comparison to other (non-point) sources of surface water pollution?; ii) Whether CSOs are relevant regarding acute pollution or rather chronic pollution of surface waters?; and iii) How different is the situation across different regions in the EU? (*cf.* Milieu, 2016; Norman, 2019; Woods-Ballard and Cherrier, 2019).

As these questions are important in the context of reviewing the effectiveness of the UWWTD, the JRC of the *European Commission* has developed a model to estimate the relevance of CSOs across EU member states (Pistocchi, 2019). This screening model attempts to help answering five key questions with regard to EU wide regulation: i) Have objectives of current regulations been achieved?; ii) Is it useful to have this regulation at EU level?; iii) Is the regulation still relevant today?; iv) Is the regulation efficient and does it provide good cost-benefits?; and v) Is the current regulation coherent with other regulations? As the evidence base to adjust such a model to local conditions is currently very weak on the EU level (Woods-Ballard and Cherrier, 2019), we recommend improving the body of evidence on CSO occurrence, pollution and impact. Examples have been reported from Germany and Switzerland (Dittmer *et al.*, 2015; Layer *et al.*, 2015; Weiss *et al.*, 2006).

Why develop a culture of evidence-based CSO compliance assessment?

Traditionally, CSOs are a pollution control measure that has been implemented with a planning-based approach. This means that, in contrast to WWTPs, which have always been subject to

substantial monitoring and performance-based compliance assessment, the approach with CSOs has been to achieve *compliance by adhering to design guidelines* or technical standards (Krejci, 2004). In recent years, advances in data communication and sensor development have been dramatically lowering the cost of data collection and now, many operators are monitoring CSOs. In some countries (UK, USA, France, parts of Germany) monitoring of large CSOs is mandatory, which effectively corresponds to a *performance-based approach*.

Triggered by the increasing availability of monitoring data, there is an ongoing debate in many countries on appropriate performance indicators for CSOs and some are even moving towards performance-based assessment, up to taxing emissions from sewer systems. However, the knowledge on ongoing activities is very fragmented, and regulatory approaches vary widely between and even within countries (Milieu, 2016). For example, in the U.S., information on whether CSO spills are occurring is being made mandatory in many states, and in several cities information on where CSO spill events are occurring are being made publicly available in real time (McMillin, 2019). In parts of Germany, monitoring is mandatory, but experience shows that data quality can be mixed, and that guidelines are not enforced by regulators on a wide basis (Hoppe *et al.*, 2019). In the UK, water utilities can make a suggestion what class their CSOs are in, before the regulating body (Environmental Agency) specifies if and how they need to be monitored. This subjectivity in regulations is occurring also in other countries, e.g. in France the operators are free to choose three different approaches to show system compliance (JO, 2015). In Denmark, no monitoring of CSOs is mandatory, but mitigation solutions are designed based on pure modelling studies of CSO, which is inevitably based on rather uncertain models. In Flanders regulation relates only to the frequency of CSO spills occurring. In Austria, tighter regulation has been under review, but due to political resistance of municipalities, this has yet not been enforced (see also Schellart, 2019).

In summary, there is, at least in the EU, a lack of culture of using and harmonising field monitoring data for compliance assessment of urban drainage systems. Although data seem to be available at the utility level, current regulations of urban drainage systems are not nearly at the same level as for WWTPs. One exception seems to be the U.S., where comprehensive long-term control plans strongly rely on data-based compliance assessment. Interestingly, rates for consumers have also increased substantially (McMillin, 2019), thought to be due to increased investment in CSO mitigating measures. This might also reflect that cities have not invested sufficiently into their wastewater infrastructure in the past.

Two important aspects regarding transitioning to compliance assessment based on monitoring data warrant further investigation. First, in case sensors that record CSO activity are installed, what metric should be reported, and at which level of aggregation? Second, how can such a compliance-based CSO assessment be designed to be both cost-effective and efficient? CSO performance assessment is complex and requires water quality-based impact assessment, e.g. as suggested in the UK's Urban Pollution Management Manual (FWR, 2012), as well as ecological expertise. In current practice, water utilities only measure water level in tank and overflow duration, in contrast to volumes or pollutant loads, as this is more straightforward and less costly. This, however, does not provide much information on the level of impact CSOs are having on the receiving surface water. In order to work out the actual impact on the receiving surface water quality, more information is needed, e.g. on the dilution ratio or the ecological sensitivity of the surface water. For this, however, more sophisticated field monitoring is necessary. Unfortunately, it is still not straightforward to monitor quality of CSO spills, or even to work out CSO spill volume from level measurements (Van Daal-Rombouts *et al.*, 2017); monitoring physico-chemical receiving water quality and advection-dispersion in receiving water is even more challenging. So although scientifically it is better to study the actual receiving water impact, in practice this would lead to high cost, sophisticated and extensive monitoring networks, with more scope for data errors or low quality data, and/or, lead to large uncertainty when receiving surface water quality models are used as well (e.g. Camacho-Suarez *et al.*, 2019). Unfortunately, research suggests that little information is contained in simple

metrics such as overflow duration and number of spills (Engelhard *et al.*, 2008). More advanced approaches suggest to also include local rainfall observations to quantify storage performance (Garbani Marcantini *et al.*, 2017; Schroeder *et al.*, 2011; Sonnenberg *et al.*, 2011).

Thus, there is a need to perform more field studies and data analyses that link problem-oriented metrics (e.g. O₂ deficits, NH₃ peaks, excessive occurrence of pesticides, etc.) to observable emissions (e.g. duration of spill or volume), and levels of uncertainty in deriving such problem-oriented metrics from field monitoring data collected at different space and time scales, using sensors of different levels of accuracy. So that CSO performance indicators based on field monitoring data can be developed in a way that is both cost-effective and with an acceptable level of uncertainty. It is furthermore important to establish field monitoring quality standards and data accreditation to ensure good data quality.

Why should water utilities tap the hidden potential of creating value from data?

Long-term, detailed monitoring studies on urban drainage flows, precipitation and combined sewer overflows are as yet rare. If they do exist, such as for example the OTHU project in Greater Lyon, France, data is not openly shared, but permission needs to be obtained on a case by case basis. Also, even in this well-studied project, serious issues with data quality remain (Bertrand-Krajewski, 2019).

Role models for sharing data are emerging (SBGE, 2019; Verbeiren *et al.*, 2019), and some utilities are self-motivated to provide yearly reports to their customers (AVA, 2018). Also, long-term control planning in the U.S. enforces transparent compliance assessment, e.g. utilities provide online access to CSO monitoring and modelling results (DC Water, 2019). Publicly available data, if done well, can generate better community ownership and awareness of urban water systems, and that value is created in very different professional domains. The example of *Flowbru.be* shows that their data have been accessed by diverse stakeholders, such as the Brussels port authority, universities, etc. (Verbeiren *et al.*, 2019). Making environmental problems more visible can also generate public engagement, see for example the 'Blue planet effect' (Gell, 2019). An example of public participation to mitigate pollution from sewers is a water utility advising people not to flush toilets during heavy rain (Sharp, 2019). Further improvement of water management cannot only be achieved through technical measures alone, but also needs public engagement and participation (Sharp, 2017).

It has been argued that CSO and sewer system monitoring does not only create additional value for the utility and regulatory authorities. In addition, long-term records of system behaviour would also be an invaluable source of information for better planning, such as city planning, pollutant load and flood risk assessment. A more accurate understanding of mass fluxes and characteristics also is important to better assess energy budgets and emerging pollutants, such as microplastics.

Given the findings of the workshop, a lack of regulatory incentive on collecting and more openly sharing CSO data currently hampers research and a better understanding in this area. Moreover, it is likely to lead to sub-optimal spending of public money on CSO pollution mitigating measures. Increasing amounts of money are being spent on monitoring, however, this is currently not being translated to better knowledge on CSO related concerns.

A centralized EU database of CSO data is very likely to generate a lot of added value for policy analysis, but questions remain as to which users this should target, what format and what level of spatial/temporal aggregation it should have for these different users, and where funding to maintain such a database would come from. Also, it needs to be discussed whether data should be provided on a mandatory or on a voluntary basis. Given the current widely variable approach to CSO regulation in different countries, the question would remain how to harmonise such a database, and how to gather and merge data across the different regions, and whether the EU should develop a

specially-tailored policy on CSOs. The Norman database (Norman, 2019) was quoted as an example of successful EU-wide database, which could provide the infrastructure for a pilot study (Bertrand-Krajewski, 2019).

However, in order to get such a database off the ground, more work needs to be done on gathering evidence for water utilities on the potential benefits of collecting and analysing more field monitoring data, as well as research on how to practically enable such a database, e.g. how such a database might be funded and maintained in the longer term.

Why the need for addressing non-technical issues?

The biggest barriers towards more sustainable management of CSOs seem not to be technical in nature, but related to policy and organisational adjustments. Similar when transitioning from argentica to digital photography, new processes have to be put in place, and utilities now have to think about new archiving and reporting new processes related to ubiquitous sensing (Blumensaat *et al.*, 2019). Technically we could put level sensors everywhere, but without providing clear aims of what information we would like to get from these sensors, we are not likely to generate much useful information from the data. Water systems are currently still seen as “Data-Rich, but Information-Poor” (DRIP) and given the problem of ‘DRIP’ has been acknowledged in the 1980s (e.g. Ward *et al.*, 1986), it is proving difficult to ‘fix the DRIP’.

During the workshop, legal issues, such as missing regulations, missing guidelines and standards, lack of enforcement, and organisational issues, such as not using data in planning, no data-based compliance assessment, no education on monitoring in universities and professional education, were all ranked higher than technical issues (SPN9, 2019).

Examples of missing incentives include the case where a UK water firm was fined for illegal overflows (BBC, 2018). While the attorney argued that a system of more than 4500 pumping stations is difficult to operate, the judge disagreed in that “more effective management, training and the establishment of a proper culture would have ensured this episode could not have happened.” In a similar fashion, Dittmer *et al.* analysed compliance data from Germany and found serious quality concerns in 60% of the mandatorily collected datasets (Dittmer *et al.*, 2015) and a Swiss study found that utilities in Switzerland do not yet widely realize the value of monitoring data for planning and compliance assessment (Manny *et al.*, 2018). A recent analysis suggests that legal or policy issues are perceived as barriers for CSO management in Switzerland and Austria (Hoppe *et al.*, 2019).

Incentives are also missing regarding jointly optimising CSOs and WWTP. Clearly, the integrated optimisation seems beneficial, because an urban drainage system is very sensitive to the wet weather treatment capacity of WWTP in terms of CSO events, and also volume (see above). Currently, in most countries, there are almost no legal incentives to maximise wet weather inflows into WWTPs, nor use monitoring data to avoid premature emptying of stored combined sewage volumes or adopt source control measures. For example, in France, the recent decree dated 21 July 2015 requires i) an integrated and coherent approach and design of both sewer systems and WWTPs (article 4) for both hydraulic and pollutant loads, and ii) a mandatory evaluation of stormwater sources control measures and their implementation where they are technically and economically efficient (article 5) (JO, 2015). It is nevertheless too early to evaluate its application and its practical consequences after only a few years.

Hence, there is a need to investigate barriers to adoption of policies related to data gathering and sharing, as well as providing stakeholders with more evidence and demonstration studies showing the benefits of monitoring data.

In addition, it is noteworthy that CSO control often leads to large investments into traditional “grey” infrastructure solutions, e.g. storage tunnels. While such systems may be straightforward solutions, they are technically very inflexible and burden society with operation and maintenance cost for many decades to come. Interestingly, water charges in the U.S. have roughly doubled in the past 15 years, and are expected to increase again by approximately 20 % in the next five years (McMillin, 2019). Hence the traditional “grey” solutions, driven by increasingly strict regulation, are coming at increasing cost of water bills to the consumers. At the same time, it is still unclear to what extent green or hybrid infrastructures can serve as more flexible solutions. New regulation should therefore allow for some flexibility of testing new methodologies, and should avoid reinforcing inflexible design and operation practices.

It is necessary to thoroughly investigate the cost-effectiveness of CSO as water pollution control. This should not only take into account the net present value, but also include the benefit of flexibility, i.e. the possibility to adapt infrastructure to a changing climate or socio-economic boundary conditions.

The IWGDM should stream future meetings and using online polling to make them interactive

Usually, the IWGDM² is meeting in the wake of relevant conferences, such as ICUD (International Conference on Urban Drainage), UDM (Urban Drainage Modelling), SPN (Sewer Processes and Networks). Unfortunately, not all members of the community are able to participate in all events. Also, a drastic reduction of business flights and international travels will be required to reduce our climate impact. Therefore, the SPN9 workshop was therefore organised as a webinar, with live streaming the presentations, which were partly given remotely from the U.S.

Polling also enabled us to assess a “learning effect” by asking the same questions before and after the workshop. Here, participants confirmed their initial vote that good data quality of a few locations is more important than monitoring all CSO tanks of a catchment with dubious quality. We found that one person is required to manage live feed and Q&A, but in general participants were reporting a satisfactory experience. The discussion initially suffered from a sub-optimal microphone, which made it difficult to follow the group discussion. A high-quality bluetooth conference-room speakerphone or mobile (throwable) microphone would have solved the problem to quickly switch from one participant to the other. Later, the discussion adapted to the boundary conditions and developed a good flow. For details on software/hardware, contact the workshop organisers.

Acknowledgements

The workshop organisers would like to acknowledge the organisers of the SPN9 conference (<http://spn9.dk/>) for enabling this workshop, and also the active engagement and input from all the workshop participants. And acknowledge all workshop presenters and contributors to the workshop organisation.

Workshop organisers and participants

Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski, INSA Lyon; Alberto Pistocchi, JRC Ispra; Alma Schellart, University Sheffield

Jörg Rieckermann, Eawag (*corresponding author: joerg.rieckermann@eawag.ch)

² International Working Group on Data and Models (IWGDM): The IWGDM is a working group of the IWA/IAHR Joint Committee on Urban Drainage (JCUD). IWGDM aims to furthering research and disseminating knowledge and technology related to data collection and modelling of urban drainage systems. This working group organises a conference known as the International Conference on Urban Drainage Modelling (UDM) <https://sites.google.com/view/iwgdm/>

Emails of the speakers and workshop participants/contributors to the position paper

a.schellart(a)sheffield.ac.uk
theo.schmitt(a)bauing.uni-kl.de
yannic.brueening(a)iswa.uni-stuttgart.de
jose.anta(a)udc.es
arbo(a)civil.aau.ak
guenter.gruber(a)tugraz.at
sbusquets(a)icra.cat
yoshinori.nishida.js(a)hitachi.com
bjoseph(a)cetaqua.com
j.a.vanderwerf(a)tudelft.nl
nevlav(a)xtra.co.nz
fzan(a)connect.ust.hk
tanguy.pouzol(a)gmail.com
jimohmodupe1(a)gmail.com
johan.vanassel(a)aquafin.be

pascale.rouault(a)kompetenz-wasser.de
j.shucksmith(a)sheffield.ac.uk
ivana.kabelkova(a)cvut.cz
holger.hoppe(a)pecher.de
luve(a)env.dtu.dk
ecullinane(a)nodwyer.com
gislain.lipeme-kouyi(a)insa-lyon.fr
sovanna.tik.1(a)ulaval.ca
naj(a)envidan.dk
arbo(a)civil.aau.dk
lisha.guo(a)ryerson.ca
m.abdel-aal(a)tees.ac.uk
pmalgratb(a)gmail.com
julia-margrit.ledergerber.1(a)ulaval.va
joerg.rieckermann(a)eawag.ch

christoph.ort(a)eawag.ch
bertrand.vallet(a)eureau.org
D.Butler(a)exeter.ac.uk
a.j.saul(a)sheffield.ac.uk
s.r.mounce(a)sheffield.ac.uk
w.shepherd(a)sheffield.ac.uk
Boud.Verbeiren(a)vub.be
morb(a)env.dtu.dk
J.G.Langeveld(a)tudelft.nl
frank.blumensaat(a)eawag.ch
Alberto.PISTOCCHI(a)ec.europa.eu
William.McMillin(a)jacobs.com
Diana Stephansen <das(a)civil.aau.dk>
jean-luc.bertrand-krajewski(a)insa-lyon.fr

References

- AVA, 2018. Geschäftsbericht 2018, Abwasserverband Altenrhein. URL: <https://www.ava-altenrhein.ch/static/uploads/2019/03/GB18.pdf>
- Badevand, 2019. Badevandsudsigten [WWW Document]. URL: <http://neworesund.badevand.dk/> (accessed 11.18.19).
- BBC, 2018. Water firm fined £2m for raw sewage leak. BBC News. URL: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-england-oxfordshire-46653684>
- Bertrand-Krajewski, J.-L., 2019. Session 3 - CSO monitoring: A joint data base for EU policy support? <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3451255>
- Camacho Suarez, V. V., Schellart, A.N.A., Brevis, W. & Shucksmith, J.D. (2019). Quantifying the impact of uncertainty within the longitudinal dispersion coefficient on concentration dynamics and regulatory compliance in rivers. *Water Resources Research*, 55, 4393–4409. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018WR023417>
- Carrington, D., 2017. Thames Water hit with record £20m fine for huge sewage leaks. *The Guardian*. URL: <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2017/mar/22/thames-water-hit-with-record-fine-for-huge-sewage-leaks>
- DC Water, 2019. DC Water - Combined sewer system [WWW Document]. URL: <https://www.dewater.com/css> (accessed 11.17.19).
- Dittmer, U., Alber, P., Seller, C., Lieb, W., 2015. Kenngrößen für die Bewertung des Betriebes von Regenüberlaufbecken. Presented at the «Jahrestagung der Lehrer und Obleute der Kläranlagen- und Kanal-Nachbarschaften des DWA-Landesverbands Baden-Württemberg» on 25./26. March 2015 (in German).
- Engelhard, C., Toffol, S.D., Rauch, W., 2008. Suitability of CSO performance indicators for compliance with ambient water quality targets. *Urban Water J.* 5, 43–49. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15730620701736902>
- Erbe, V., Risholt, L.P., Schilling, W., Londong, J., 2002. Integrated modelling for analysis and optimisation of wastewater systems – the Odenthal case. *Urban Water* 4, 63–71. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1462-0758\(01\)00060-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1462-0758(01)00060-7)
- F. W. R., 2012. Urban pollution management manual 3rd edition. URL: <http://www.fwr.org/UPM3>
- Garbani Marcantini, L., Cereghetti, G., Muschalla, D., Regneri, M., Schegg, S., Rieckermann, J., 2017. Playing the rain: a chess-based rating algorithm for the performance assessment of real-time control in urban drainage networks. Presented at the ICUD 2017, Prague.
- Garneau, C., Vanrolleghem, P.A., 2017. Développement d'un modèle de prévision de la qualité de l'eau. *Vecteur Environ.*, March 2017.
- Gell, F., 2019. The Blue Planet effect: the plastics revolution is just the start. *The Guardian*, 25th March 2019. <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2019/mar/25/plastics-revolution-marine-life>

- Hoppe, H., Dittmer, U., Gruber, G., Rieckermann, J., 2019. Datenbasierte Planungs-, Betriebs- und Vollzugskonzepte zur nachhaltigen Regenwasserbehandlung. 52. Essener Tagung für Wasserwirtschaft. March, 20-22, 2019. Aachen. 250, 26 (16 pp.).
- JO, 2015. Arrêté du 21 juillet 2015 relatif aux systèmes d'assainissement collectif et aux installations d'assainissement non collectif, à l'exception des installations d'assainissement non collectif recevant une charge brute de pollution organique inférieure ou égale à 1,2 kg/j de DBO5. Journal Officiel de la République Française, 19 août 2015, 25 p. Updated version available at <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000031052756&categorieLien=id> (accessed on 03 March 2020).
- Krejci, V., 2004. Konzepte des Gewässerschutzes. GWA Gas Wasser Abwasser 6, 423-430.
- Layer, M., Dittmer, U., Lieb, W., 2015. Emissionsorientierte Erfolgskontrolle basierend auf dem Betriebsverhalten von Behandlungsanlagen. Presented at the Conference Aqua Urbanica. Stuttgart, Germany.
- Manny, L., Fischer, M., Rieckermann, J., 2018. Policy Analysis for Better Protection of Receiving Waters during Wet Weather. Presented at the 11th International Conference on Urban Drainage Modelling, September 23 –26, 2018., Palermo, Italy, p. 4.
- McMillin, W., 2019. Session 1.2 - Combined Sewer Overflows in the US. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3451255>
- Meng, F., Fu, G., Butler, D., 2016. Water quality permitting: From end-of-pipe to operational strategies. Water Res. 101, 114–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2016.05.078>
- Milieu, 2016. Final Report. Assessment of impact of storm water overflows from combined wastewater collecting systems on water bodies (including the marine environment) in the 28 EU Member States. (No. Specific Contract No. 070201/2014/SFRA/693725/ENV/C.2).
- Norman, 2019. Contaminants of Emerging Concern in Urban Wastewater - Joint NORMAN and Water Europe Position Paper. https://www.normandata.eu/sites/default/files/files/Publications/Position%20paper_CECs%20UWW_NORMAN_WE_2019_Final_20190910_public.pdf (accessed 11.18.19)
- Pistocchi, A., 2019. Session 2.1 - Combined sewer overflows: a EU wide perspective. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3451255>
- SBGE, 2019. Bienvenue sur flowbru! — Français [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.flowbru.be/fr> (accessed 11.18.19).
- Schellart, A., 2019. Session 1.1 - Current developments in different countries regarding the assessment of CSOs. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3451255>
- Schroeder, K., Riechel, M., Matzinger, A., Rouault, P., Sonnenberg, H., Pawlowsky-Reusing, E., Gnirss, R., 2011. Evaluation of effectiveness of combined sewer overflow control measures by operational data. Water Sci. Technol. 63(2), 325–330. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2011.058>
- Schütze, M., Campisano, A., Colas, H., Schilling, W., Vanrolleghem, P.A., 2004. Real time control of urban wastewater systems—where do we stand today? J. Hydrol. 299, 335–348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2004.08.010>
- Seggelke, K., Löwe, R., Beeneken, T., Fuchs, L., 2013. Implementation of an integrated real-time control system of sewer system and wastewater treatment plant in the city of Wilhelmshaven. Urban Water J. 10, 330–341. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1573062X.2013.820331>
- Sharp, L., 2017. Reconnecting people and water: Public engagement and sustainable urban water management. 1st Ed., London, Routledge, <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315851679>
- Sharp, L., 2019. Why people in a flooded British town were told to stop flushing the toilet. The Conversation, June 20th, 2019. <https://theconversation.com/why-people-in-a-flooded-british-town-were-told-to-stop-flushing-the-toilet-119115> (accessed 11.18.19)
- Sonnenberg, H., Pawlowsky-Reusing, R., Riechel, M., Caradot, N., Toth, E., Matzinger, A., Rouault, P., 2011. Different methods of CSO identification in sewer systems and receiving waters. Presented at the 12th International Conference on Urban Drainage, Porto Alegre, Brazil.
- SPN9, 2019. SPN9 CSO workshop - Votes from interactive polls. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3385405>
- UK Environment Agency, 2019. Thames Water fined £2m for “foreseeable and avoidable” pollution [WWW Document]. GOV.UK. URL <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/thames-water-fined-2m-for-foreseeable-and-avoidable-pollution> (accessed 11.18.19).

- UK Environment Agency, 2017. Thames Water ordered to pay record £20 million for river pollution [WWW Document]. GOV.UK. URL <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/thames-water-ordered-to-pay-record-20-million-for-river-pollution> (accessed 5.14.18).
- Van Daal-Rombouts, P., Tralli, A., Verhaart, F., Langeveld, J., Clemens, F., 2017. Validation of computational fluid dynamics for deriving weir discharge relationships with scale model experiments and prototype measurements. *Flow Measurement and Instrumentation*, 58, 52-61.
doi: 10.1016/j.flowmeasinst.2017.09.011
- Vanrolleghem, P.A., Benedetti, L., Meirlaen, J., 2005. Modelling and real-time control of the integrated urban wastewater system. *Environ. Model. Softw.* 20, 427–442.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2004.02.004>
- Verbeiren, B., Bazier, G., Pireaux, D., 2019. MESURER L'EAU EN VILLE : 15 ANS D'EXPÉRIENCE EN MATIÈRE D' AUTOSURVEILLANCE À BRUXELLES, in: *Fonctionnement Des Systèmes d'assainissement*. Presented at the Colloque Fonctionnement des systèmes d'assainissement : l'arrêté du 21 juillet 2015... esprit et pratiques, 5 et 6 février 2019, Association Scientifique et Technique pour l'Eau et l'Environnement (Astee), Colombes, F. (in French).
- Ward, R.C., Loftis, J.C. and McBride, G.B., 1986. The 'Data rich but Information poor' Syndrome in Water Quality Monitoring', *Environmental Management*, 10, 3, pp 291-297.
- Weiss, G., Brombach, H., Wöhrle, C., 2006. Monitoring of Combined Sewer Overflow Tanks: Results of 500 Years of Measurement Records. *Water Pract. Technol.* 1. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wpt.2006.011>
- Woods-Ballard, B., Cherrier, V., 2019. Review of the UWWTD implementation, and the treatment of CSOs in the EU, in: *CIWEM UDG AUTUMN CONFERENCE 2019*. Presented at the CIWEM Urban Drainage Group Autumn conference 2019 04 November 2019 - 06 November 2019, CIWEM, East Midlands, UK